

Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

NRT Sentinel 4

Total Column Water Vapour

Document approval record

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AC SAF	Atmospheric Composition Monitoring Satellite Application Facility
AMF	Air Mass Factor, or optical enhancement factor
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
DLR	German Aerospace Centre
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
Envisat	Environmental Satellite
ESA	European Space Agency
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FCI	Flexible Combined Imager
GDP	GOME Data Processor
GE_LER	Geometry-dependent effective Lambertian equivalent reflectivity
GEMS	Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer
GOME	Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment
IASI	Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer
IRS	Infrared Sounder
OCA	Optimal Cloud Analysis
OCRA	Optical Cloud Recognition Algorithm
OMI	Ozone Monitoring Instrument
MLER	Minimum Lambertian equivalent reflectivity
MTG-S	Meteosat Third Generation-Sounding mission
NIR	Near InfraRed
RAL	Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
ROCINN	Retrieval of Cloud Information using Neural Networks
RRS	Rotational Raman Scattering
S4	Sentinel-4
S5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SCD	Slant Column Density
SCIAMACHY	Scanning Imaging Absorption spectroMeter for Atmospheric CHartography
TEMIS	Tropospheric Emission Monitoring Internet Service
TEMPO	Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution
TROPOMI	TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument
UVN	Ultraviolet-Visible-Near Infrared
UVVIS	Ultraviolet-Visible
VCD	Vertical Column Density
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

INTRODUCTION TO EUMETSAT SATELLITE APPLICATION FACILITY ON ATMOSPHERIC COMPOSITION MONITORING (AC SAF)

Background

Monitoring atmospheric chemistry is essential. Human-induced and natural changes in the atmosphere and hazards, such as global warming, loss of stratospheric ozone, increasing UV radiation and pollution, require continuous monitoring, following international protocols and guidelines set forth by policymakers. This monitoring is the task for EUMETSAT.

Objectives

The main objectives of the AC SAF is to process, archive, validate and disseminate to policymakers and to the wide public atmospheric composition products (O₃, NO₂, SO₂, BrO, HCHO, H₂O, OClO, CO, NH₃), aerosol products and surface ultraviolet radiation products utilising EUMETSAT satellites. The majority of the AC SAF products are based on data from the GOME-2 and IASI instruments onboard the MetOp platforms and expand on the upcoming Copernicus missions Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5. Another important task, besides the near real-time (NRT) and offline data dissemination, is the provision of long-term, high-quality atmospheric composition products resulting from reprocessing activities in form of climate data records (CDR).

Product categories, timeliness and dissemination

NRT products are available in less than three hours after measurement. These products are disseminated via EUMETCast, WMO GTS or internet.

- Near real-time trace gas columns (total and tropospheric O₃ and NO₂, total SO₂, total HCHO, CO, H₂O) and high-resolution ozone profiles
- Near real-time absorbing aerosol indexes from main science channels and polarization measurement detectors
- Near real-time UV indexes, clear-sky and cloud-corrected

Offline products are available within two weeks after measurement and disseminated via dedicated web services at EUMETSAT and AC SAF.

- Offline trace gas columns (total and tropospheric O₃ and NO₂, total SO₂, total BrO, total HCHO, total H₂O) and high-resolution ozone profiles
- Offline absorbing aerosol indexes from main science channels and polarization measurement detectors
- Offline surface UV, daily doses and daily maximum values with several weighting functions

(Climate) Data records are available after reprocessing activities from the EUMETSAT Data Centre and/or the AC SAF archives.

- Data records generated in reprocessing
- Lambertian-equivalent reflectivity
- Total OclO, NO₂, H₂O

Users can access the AC SAF offline products and data records (free of charge) by registering at the AC SAF web site.

More information about the AC SAF project, products and services: <https://acsaf.org/>

AC SAF Helpdesk: helpdesk@acsaf.org X: https://x.com/Atmospheric_SAF

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/acsaf.bsky.social>

A. INTRODUCTION

A.1. Scope of this document

Atmospheric water vapour is the most important natural greenhouse gas in the troposphere, accounting for more than 60% of the greenhouse effect (Clough and Iacono, 1995; Kiehl and Trenberth, 1997). Despite this importance, its roles in climate and its reactions to climate change are still difficult to assess. As the atmosphere warms, water vapour is expected to rise faster than the total precipitation amount, which is governed by the surface heat budget through evaporation (Trenberth and Stepaniak, 2003). This results in a positive water vapour feedback that further amplifies the original warming effect (Colman, 2003; Soden et al., 2005; Soden and Held, 2006). On the other hand, clouds are known to have positive effects on cooling the earth's surface (Bellomo et al., 2014; Brown et al., 2016). However, the net cooling or warming effect of clouds in a continuous warming atmosphere is not yet well understood (Boucher et al., 2013). To investigate these complex interactions and evaluate climate models, continuous monitoring of the spatio-temporal variations of total column water vapour (TCWV) on a global scale is necessary (Hartmann et al., 2013).

This document describes the Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) of the retrieval of total column water vapour from measurements of the Sentinel-4 payload onboard the Meteosat Third Generation-Sounding mission (MTG-S). The algorithm consists of two major steps. The first step is the retrieval of water vapour slant columns. The second step is the conversion of the water vapour slant columns to vertical columns. The purpose of the ATBD is to provide detailed mathematical and physical descriptions of the algorithm, along with discussions of algorithm inputs and outputs, data products, algorithm validation and error analysis. The ATBD also includes a summary description of the Sentinel-4 payload and the anticipated changes from heritage algorithms.

A.2 Acknowledgements

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[TBD]

1. INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION

1.1 Sentinel-4/UVN

Sentinel-4 is an operational satellite mission providing atmospheric composition data for the extended European region with a hourly revisit time in support of the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). The instrument onboard Sentinel-4 is the Ultraviolet-Visible-Near-infrared (UVN) spectrometer that will be carried on the geostationary MTG-S platforms. The satellites' nominal pointing geolocation is 45° N, 0° W. The first MTG-S platform is expected to be launched and to reach the landing orbit around Q3/2025 with a twin platform around 2029. The instrument measurement concept combines a scan mirror with a push-broom design. A mirror scanning from east to west captures the light from a narrow strip on the Earth running in the north-to-south direction and reflects it into the telescope. The telescope system in turn images the strip onto the slits of the ultraviolet and visible (UVVIS) and near-infrared (NIR) spectrometer channels. The across-slit dimension is collapsed into a spectral dimension and spectra are recorded by two-dimensional Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) detectors. The UVN instrument covers the visible wavelength range with a spectral resolution of about 0.5 nm at a sampling ratio of three.

Sentinel-4 belongs to the family of already flown UVN spectrometers (SCIAMACHY, OMI, GOME, and GOME-2) and of those spectrometers recently launched (TROPOMI) and currently under development (Sentinel-5). Sentinel-4 will be the first mission carrying a UVN imaging spectrometer in a geostationary orbit over Europe. Other similar spectrometers are the Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution (TEMPO) mission (Zoogman et al., 2016), which covers the North American extended region, and the Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer (GEMS; Kim, 2020), which covers the East Asian extended region. A clear synergy between geostationary observations and observations by similar spectrometers in polar orbits is expected.

1.2 Observational geometry

The spatial sampling distance varies across the geographic coverage area due to projection and curvature effects and is about 8 x 8 km at a reference location at 45° N and the satellite's nominal longitude. There are 551 pixels in the north-to-south direction and about 580 pixels in a single east-to-west scan. A daily Earth observation will consist of about 16 to 20 one-hour east-to-west scans with fast retraces in-between. The total area covered in a single day by Sentinel-4 is the European extended region. The area captured by a single one-hour scan is smaller and varies within the geographic coverage area in a systematic way depending on the time of day and season. Most importantly for absorption spectroscopy algorithms for Sentinel-4, a westward shift in the afternoon has to be expected. This has the consequence of increasingly including the North Atlantic region into the field-of-view only for the second half of the day. Typical viewing zenith angles and solar zenith angles for Sentinel-4 are illustrated in Figure 1.

Throughout this document we refer to the Sentinel-4 satellite instrument as UVN interchangeably. We call the east-to-west scanning direction the along-track or across-slit direction and the north-to-south direction the across-track or along-slit direction.

Finally, we adopt the project convention that rows of the two-dimensional CCD correspond to the different viewing directions (the across-track dimension of the CCD) and columns to the different wavelengths (the spectral dimension of the CCD).

Figure 1: (a) Solar zenith angle for June 20, 7:00 UTC and (b) for 19:00 UTC. (c) Relative azimuth angle at 19:00 UTC; (d) Viewing zenith angle at sea level across the Sentinel-4 entire geographic coverage area. The satellite central pointing is at 0°W and 45°N. The position of the satellite will vary slightly while in orbit with a north-to-south amplitude of about 2° and an east-to-west amplitude of about 0.5°. At the eastern and western edges of the geographic coverage area only about half of the CCD rows correspond to line-of-sights that actually hit the Earth's surface. The area covered by a single one-hour scan is smaller than the geographic coverage area and varies in a systematic way. Most significant is a large westward shift in the afternoon.

1.3 Radiometry

Sentinel-4's UVN payload is a CCD-based push-broom imaging spectrometer which will record backscattered light in the UV (305 – 400 nm), Vis (400 – 500 nm) part of the electromagnetic spectrum for the retrieval of mainly (trace) gas columns and aerosols and in the NIR (750 – 775 nm) for the coincident retrieval of mainly cloud and aerosol properties. The main design specifications of the UVN payload, together with the radiometric, calibration and polarization requirements set forth by ESA, are provided in Table 1. The two bands differ in spectral resolution with the UVVIS having 0.5 nm and the NIR 0.12 nm. This is because the NIR band is characterized by the strongest

absorption band by molecular oxygen (758 – 770 nm) showing considerable spectral structure variations and dynamic range (see right panel in Figure 2) when compared to the UVVIS range. Accordingly, the instrumental response function (ISRF) for both bands differ (Figure 3) being the ISRF full-width half-maximum in the NIR 1/3 of that in the UVVIS.

Figure 2: Spectral radiance for Sentinel-4 UVVIS and NIR bands for a clear sky and cloudy scene.

Figure 3: Sentinel-4/UVN Instrumental response function for (a) two wavelengths in the UVVIS water vapor absorption band and one in the oxygen A-band at center FOV; (b) for the leftmost, central and rightmost ground pixel rows at the central water vapor wavelength. Panel (b) illustrates the CCD smile effect along the spatial dimension.

1.4 Polarization

The polarization state of light reaching the sensor is described by the incident Stokes vector $\vec{I}^T = (I, Q, U, V)$. The Stokes parameters of a plane electromagnetic wave are always defined with respect to a reference plane containing the direction of wave propagation. This plane is also called the principal plane. The Müller matrix M is a 4×4 matrix describing the transformation from incident to outgoing Stokes vectors as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \\ V \end{pmatrix}_{out} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & M_{14} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} & M_{24} \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} & M_{34} \\ M_{41} & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \\ V \end{pmatrix}_{inc} \quad (1)$$

The transformation of Eq. 1 implies a rotation of the reference frame such that the atmospheric reference frame to the optical reference frame are connected by:

$$\vec{L}(\eta) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(2\eta) & -\sin(2\eta) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(2\eta) & -\cos(2\eta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where η is the angle of rotation between the two frames $\vec{I}_{out}^T = \vec{L}(\eta) M \vec{I}_{inc}^T$.

The angle of rotation can be calculated with the Stokes vector solving the following:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{atan} \frac{U}{Q} \quad (3)$$

$$\operatorname{sign}(\cos 2\eta) = \operatorname{sign} Q$$

the angle of polarization α and the rotation introduced by the operator \vec{L} are connected. Customary conventions are that the direct solar beam is unpolarized, that is $\vec{I}^T = (1, 0, 0, 0)$. and that skylight is most polarized when measured at 90° away for the (solar) principal plane. In this configuration $\alpha = \eta - \eta' = \eta - 90^\circ$.

We can assume that the individual elements of the Mueller matrices are normalized to retain information on polarization, independently of absolute intensity. This implies that:

$$m_{ij} = \frac{M_{ij}}{M_{11}}. \quad (4)$$

M_{11} describes reflected intensity for unpolarized light, but the actual reflectance depends on the incoming light polarization state, which we know is polarized by the atmosphere (molecules, aerosols, water droplets, and ice crystals) and surface in the solar range. This implies that the elements of interest in the right hand side of Eq. 1 are the first row. While Rayleigh scattering is always perpendicular to the scattering plane, Mie scattering from atmospheric particles can be either parallel or perpendicular. This makes the angle of polarization between the principal plane and the measurement reference frame important.

If we neglect $\pi/4$ and circular polarized light ($U, V \rightarrow 0$) we can express the Stokes vector as $\vec{I}^T = (I, Q, 0, 0)$ and introducing the degree of linear polarization $\mu = Q/I$ ($0 \leq \mu \leq 1$), the Stokes vector is written as $\vec{I}^T = (I, \mu I, 0, 0)$.

By doing this, we are saying that the incident Stokes vector is parallel polarized ($I = I_{\parallel}$) and the electric field oscillates along the principal plane. Therefore, the uncalibrated intensity measured by

a polarization-sensitive sensor is given by the calibrated intensity I_λ plus terms describing the errors introduced by the sensors's polarization sensitivity as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{\lambda,uncal} &= \int F_\lambda * (M_{\lambda,11} I_\lambda + M_{\lambda,12} Q_\lambda \cos 2\eta - M_{\lambda,13} Q_\lambda \sin 2\eta) d\lambda \\
 &\rightarrow M_{\lambda,11} \int F_\lambda * (I_\lambda + m_{\lambda,12} Q_\lambda \cos 2\eta - m_{\lambda,13} Q_\lambda \sin 2\eta) d\lambda
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where F_λ is the instrument response function and * is convolution.

Without knowledge of α, η once can only assume that both angles and μ are varying slowly within some spectral ranges in which the gas species have a weak absorption band. This assumption does not hold, for instance, for the Fraunhofer lines. In this case, the pseudo cross-sections can be written as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\int F_\lambda * m_{1,j} E_{0,\lambda} d\lambda}{\int F_\lambda * E_{0,\lambda} d\lambda} \tag{6}$$

where $E_{0,\lambda}$ is the spectral irradiance.

AIRBUS/ESA provided information on the polarisation effects for Sentinel-4 observations [RD03]. The information is based on 108 measurements with 10° step each ($3 \times 360^\circ$ in total). The on ground measured polarization sensitivity is plotted in Figure 4. The pseudo cross-sections for the DOAS retrievals have been generated based on the provided dataset.

Figure 4: Spectral polarization sensitivity at the center of the FOV for (a) UVVIS and (b) NIR Sentinel-4 bands

The polarisation file by AIRBUS contains the Müller Matrix element 1,2 and 1,3. The non diagonal matrix elements describe the effects of the optical system on polarisation of incoming light. Sentinel-4 has 551 individual detector-rows (the spatial dimension) and the polarisation effects are given for 3 rows (i.e. y_centre_uvvis , 57, 296, 535 or central FOV $\pm 1.75^\circ$) and for 213 binned wavelengths. The full spectral resolution in the UVVIS range is 1260 pixels (between 300 and 500 nm).

To generate polarisation pseudo cross-sections, two interpolations and extrapolations are performed: 1) from the 213 binned wavelength to 1260 detector wavelength; 2) to cover the full

spatial dimension of 551 rows based on the three given. Before the interpolations and convolutions, the broadband structures were subtracted. This step is not necessary, but its application in DOAS will not cause additional issues and makes the interpolation in the spatial dimension smoother. For this purpose a 12th (3rd for NIR) order polynomial was fitted to Müller matrix elements and subtracted afterwards.

Müller matrix elements (central FOV)

Figure 5: Element of the Müller matrix for the (a) UVVIS and (b) NIR bands of Sentinel-4 at the center FOV. Dashed line are the fitted polynomials that are subtracted for the computation of the pseudo cross-sections.

The resulting polarisation array contains small scale spectral features that might potentially affect the DOAS retrieval. However, the spectral resolution is very coarse compared to the measured spectra. For the spectral interpolation a linear interpolation seems insufficient and a quadratic interpolation might fit better to the scope. The interpolation (Figure 5) was performed to the spectral grid of the high resolution solar spectrum (SAO2010).

Pseudo cross-sections UVVIS

Figure 6: Polarization-induced pseudo cross-sections and HITRAN line intensities for water vapor

The final pseudo cross-sections to be added to the specific gas species are plotted in Figure 6. They show non negligible spectral features in the range of 450-480 nm. This will affect the glyoxal (433 - 465 nm), NO₂ (425 - 497 nm) retrievals but also water vapour (430 - 460 nm).

[**impact on TCWV to be assessed**]

Table 1: Summary of the Sentinel-4/UVN instrument main design, requirements [Riedl et al., 2018], and most recent performance parameters [Bazalgette Courrèges-Lacoste et al., 2022]

Spectral			
Parameter	UVVIS	NIR	Comments
Wavelength range	305-500 nm	750-775 nm	
Resolution / Oversampling	0.5 nm / 3	0.12 nm / 3	Oversampling equals resolution divided by spectral pixel sampling
Calibration accuracy	0.0017 nm	0.0020 nm	
Geometric and temporal coverage			
Spatial sampling distance (SSD)	8 km x 8 km (E/W x N/S)		On-ground projected SSD at sub-satellite point (45°N, 0°W)
Integrated Energy	70% over 1.47 * 1.13 SSD 90% over 1.72 * 1.72 SSD		IE is a measure of the spatial resolution
North-to-South slit FOV	4.0°		
Daily Earth observation time	Summer 01:40 – 21:40 (maximum) Winter 03:40 – 19:40 (minimum)		UTC Time
Spatial co-registration	Intra-detector 10% SSD Inter-detector 20% SSD		2-dimensional absolute co-registration (E/W and N/S)
Radiometric			
Optical throughput	50%	60%	End-to-end scanner-detector
Earthshine SNR	UV > 160 Vis > 1600	NIR > 600 O ₂ A band > 90	
Earthshine absolute accuracy	< 3%	< 3%	Radiance and reflectance
Solar absolute accuracy	< 3%	< 3%	Irradiance
Polarization sensitivity	< 1%	< 1%	
Spectral relative accuracy	< 0.05%	< 0.5%	Reflectance only, 3 nm width (UVVIS) and 7.5 nm (NIR)
Spatial relative accuracy	< 0.25%	< 0.25%	Earthshine radiance and reflectance

2. ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

2.1 Heritage

The ACSAF H₂O algorithm implemented for the Sentinel-4 mission is the latest update of algorithms based on the classical Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS) method as first applied at measurements of the GOME-2 sensor series (Grossi et al., 2015, Chan et al., 2020) and, successively, to the TROPOMI instrument on Sentinel-5 precursor (Chan et al., 2022). One notable feature of the algorithm is that it does not include explicit numerical modelling of the atmospheric radiative transfer. The algorithm consists of three basic steps: (1) DOAS fitting, (2) non-linearity absorption correction and (3) vertical column density calculation (Wagner et al., 2003, 2006).

In the first step, slant columns of H₂O and O₂ are derived from the differential absorption structures. For GOME-2 the step used the NIR wavelength region 614 – 683 nm, while for TROPOMI also the UVVIS range around 450 nm was exploited. The NIR wavelength range captures the strongest molecular absorption band by water vapor. However, this will not be available for Sentinel-4 and a new wavelength region will be used (see later Sections). Since the highly fine structured H₂O (and O₂) absorption bands cannot be spectroscopically resolved by sensors with the current spectral resolution, saturation in some absorption lines will lead to a situation in which the retrieved slant columns are no longer a linear function of the atmospheric H₂O and O₂ column density.

In the second step, a correction for these non-linearity effects is applied using model results from line-by-line calculations of a representative atmosphere. Finally, the conversion from slant columns to vertical columns is performed using an air mass factor for H₂O based on the retrieved air mass factor of O₂, in conjunction with an AMF correction factor. The O₂ AMF is derived from the measurement as the fitted O₂ slant column divided by the O₂ vertical column density, which is a known quantity as oxygen is a well-mixed gas with vertically-constant mixing ratio. The AMF correction factor, which accounts for different height profiles of H₂O and O₂, uses a look-up table for geometric correction and a correction polynomial for the AMF dependence on surface albedo.

The algorithm deliberately uses a minimum of external input to generate a data set, being truly independent from model outputs and from other observational records. Therefore, a single temperature has been preliminarily used for the DOAS cross-sections, a single H₂O vertical profile for the AMF correction factor, and the only external information comes from a surface albedo database. Note also that the retrieval uses a spectral window below the vegetation red-edge peak. This setting minimizes albedo changes due to vegetation growth. Due to the strength of the H₂O and O₂ absorptions and due to the flexibility of the DOAS spectral fitting, the TCWV product is expected to be insensitive to instrument degradation and/or drift.

The greatest limiting factor for accuracy of the H₂O vertical column density is contamination by clouds. In the latest version of the GOME-2 retrieval algorithm (Grossi et al., 2015), two clouds indicators are used to identify and remove cloudy pixels. The first cloud flag is set if the product of cloud fraction and cloud-top albedo exceeds a given threshold (anomalously high cloud-top reflection if the product is bigger than 0.6). The second H₂O cloud flag is set if the retrieved O₂ slant column density (SCD) is below 80% of the maximum O₂ SCD for the respective solar zenith angle (because the main part of the O₂ column should be present for a useful TCWV measurement).

2.2 Adaptation of heritage algorithm to Sentinel-4/UVN

The GOME-2 fitting window in the NIR part of the spectrum, at 614–683 nm, is neither available to Sentinel-4 nor to Sentinel-5 (and neither to OMI and Sentinel-5 precursor). This is illustrated in Figure 7, which shows the H₂O absorption for the spectral range of GOME-2, with the spectral ranges of Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5. Common to all three instruments are water vapour bands in the UVVIS region about 430–480 nm. For Sentinel-5, a possible alternative would be a window around 700 nm. Although it is not strictly necessary to use the same wavelength region for each instrument, spectral consistency among different instruments is preferred because of the envisioned creation of merged data records of climatological relevance. The stability and accuracy of multi-sensor data records rely on the avoidance of discontinuity between individual H₂O time series arising from different spectrally-dependent light penetration depths and different sensitivities on surface reflectivity.

Figure 7: Water vapor absorption bands in the UVVIS-NIR spectral range, together with the spectral coverage of sensors dedicated to the retrieval of vertical columns (Chan et al., 2020)

Figure 7 shows also that the water vapour absorption in the UVVIS spectral range is much weaker than in the NIR spectral range. This may be expected to lead to larger uncertainties on the retrieved SCDs. However, an advantage of the weak absorption is that no corrections for spectral saturation effects are necessary. Saturation effects at 442 nm have been assessed to amount up to 2% of the total gaseous optical depth and are deemed negligible (Lampel et al., 2015). A second advantage is

that the contrast in surface reflectivity between land and ocean is comparatively small than in the NIR, making the retrieved H₂O data sets more consistent across land-ocean boundaries. Second, in the UVVIS spectral range the sensitivity for atmospheric layer close to the surface is higher, due to the higher ocean albedo and, because of the stronger Rayleigh scattering, the effects of clouds is smaller than at longer wavelengths. As downside, there is no nearby O₂ band which may be used to derive the AMF. Thus the AMF must be based entirely on radiative transfer calculations, which sets higher requirements on the accuracy of the geophysical input parameters such as surface albedo and H₂O profile.

The ACSAF algorithm currently in use for the retrieval of the GOME-2 product is implemented in UPAS, a pre-existent level 2 processing software system at DLR ([RD04, RD05]). It is straightforward to adapt the DOAS spectral fitting (SCD retrieval) to the UVVIS retrieval window by changing the input parameters, and by providing the applicable H₂O cross-sections and auxiliary fit components, upon convolution with the respective instrument slit functions. The wavelength interval between 430 and 480 nm is chosen as it leads to the smallest retrieval uncertainties (Wang et al., 2014). The retrieval window includes the water vapour feature at about 442 nm and also the weaker absorption feature at about 470 nm.

The AMF employed for the conversion from SCD to vertical column density can be described as a function of “scattering weights” and a “shape factor” (Gonzales et al., 2015). In the operational retrieval, a pre-calculated look-up table for the scattering weights will be used, similar to the operational GOME-2 NO₂ retrieval. The shape factor will be based on representative water vapour profiles (see later section on the implementation for TROPOMI on Sentinel-5 precursor). The scattering weights have to be calculated separately for the viewing conditions of each instrument. For this calculation the radiative transfer model VLIDORT (Spurr 2008) or SCIATRAN (Rozanov et al., 2014) can be used. The scattering weights are wavelength-dependent but vary slowly in the UVVIS spectral range, such that it is safe to compute them at the fixed 442 nm channel.

The look-up tables will be parameterised by the surface albedo with entries for solar zenith angles, viewing zenith angles, relative azimuth angles, and altitude levels and cloud top- and surface pressure. As in the NIR spectral range retrieval, surface albedo (snow) and cloud cover can lead to significant errors in the AMF. Therefore, as for the GOME-2 retrieval (Grossi et al., 2015), a cloud indicator will be used to identify and flag cloudy pixels.

2.3 Feasibility of H₂O retrieval in the UVVIS spectral region

Previous studies investigating the feasibility of the retrieval of the water vapour in the UVVIS spectral range have demonstrated that the errors associated to the retrieved H₂O SCD are quite small. Typical uncertainties for GOME-2 and OMI measurements are in the range between 1-5 *10²² molecules/cm², depending on the instrument ground pixel size (Wagner et al., 2013). Because of the much smaller absorption cross section, the water vapour columns derived in the UVVIS spectral range have typically larger uncertainties compared to those derived in the red spectral range. However, the uncertainties in the AMF retrieval due to variations in surface albedo and cloud fractions are smaller in the UVVIS than in the NIR, especially over ocean. Wang et al. (2014) found a relative median uncertainties in the H₂O SCD of 11% and a reasonable agreement when comparing monthly mean OMI water vapour columns computed in the UVVIS spectral range with MODIS NIR data, GlobVapour combined MERIS + SSM/I product and AERONET measurements.

Rather than comparing monthly means from different instruments, a direct comparison of water vapour retrievals in the UVVIS and NIR spectral regions using single spectra from the GOME-2A

instrument is advantageous. Spectral retrievals in the NIR were performed by the algorithm used also for the AC-SAF GOME-2 product. For the UVVIS region the following settings for the DOAS retrieval have been employed: spectral region 427.7 – 465 nm; GOME-2A measured solar spectrum (as reference spectrum); cross-sections H₂O HITEMP at 293K, NO₂ at 220 K (Vandaele et al., 2002), O₃ at 228K (Brion et al. 1998), O₄ at 293K (Thalman and Volkamer et al., 2013), liquid water (Pope et al., 1997); and eventually a Ring reference spectrum.

Figure 8: Water vapour total column for one day of GOME-2A data. From top to bottom: ECMWF reanalysis model, GOME-2A NIR retrievals, GOME-2A UVVIS retrievals.

The AMF lookup table was calculated as described in Section 2.6. An initial H₂O profile shape has been derived from a subset of 6 years of ECMWF ERA-interim model data. The profiles were averaged for each month and binned for latitude, longitude, and TCWV (5 bins). The calculation of the shape factor for each measurement is iterative: first the shape factor is calculated using the average profile of all 5 TCWV bins. Then the TCWV retrieved from GOME-2 is used to interpolate

the profile from the closest TCWV bins, and the AMF calculation is repeated. For the vast majority of cases one iteration appeared to be sufficient (convergence criterium 1% on TCWV). It is anticipated that either ERA-5 reanalysis or coincident water vapour profiles derived by the infrared sounder (IRS) instrument on board the MTG-S platform (Holmlund et al., 2021).

Figure 9: GOME-2 TCWV from the blue UVVIS region, versus GOME-2 TCWV from the red NIR region (left panel) and versus the model (right panel). Data from Figure 8.

Figure 10: All GOME-2 data points from Figure 8 as function of latitude. Solid lines are averages per latitude bin: red line: retrieval from red region; blue line: retrieval from blue region; black line: corresponding ECMWF reanalysis data.

The results are shown in the figures below, which are based on data of 14 GOME-2A orbits on January first, 2008. Figure 8 shows TCWV retrieved from the NIR region (centre panel) and from the UVVIS region (lower panel). As comparison, ECMWF reanalysis data are shown (top panel). Both retrievals yield very similar spatial structures, which correlate well to the structures from the

model. The GOME-2 TCWV from the NIR region has a slightly smoother appearance than TCWV from the blue region. More noise on the SCDs from the UVVIS region is to be expected, due to the smaller H₂O absorption cross-section.

A scatterplot between UVVIS and NIR retrievals is shown in Figure 9 left panel. At TCWV values of 20-30 kg/m² both retrievals yield comparable results (apart from the scatter). For low TCWV values, the UVVIS region on average yields higher values, whereas for high TCWV there is a slight tendency for the blue region to yield lower values. A comparison of blue region retrievals against the ECMWF reanalysis model is shown in Figure 9, right panel. At low TCWV values, blue region retrievals are systematically higher. At around 20-25 kg/m², blue region retrievals are slightly lower. This feature is also seen in other comparisons using OMI data (Wang et al., 2014), whereas for higher TCWV values the UVVIS retrievals yield again slightly higher values than modelled ones.

Figure 10 shows the zonal average TCWV values per latitude bin. At Arctic and sub-Arctic latitudes, blue retrievals are systematically higher than red region retrievals. This results is in line with the bias for low TCWV values. A good comparison is found in the tropical regions where both retrievals yield higher TCWV than the model. In the results presented here, the cloud rejection algorithm used was quite straightforward, rejecting everything with cloud radiance fraction > 0.5. Initial tests with a more stringent cloud rejection criterium did not significantly reduce the scatter between the methods but did change their relative bias. A different choice of a priori H₂O profiles for the AMF calculation also impacts the bias.

This initial test shows that retrievals from the blue region yield similar TCWV results as retrievals from the red region with the possible exception of the Arctic. We can confidently conclude that the retrieval of water vapour from the blue UVVIS region is feasible for Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5. Further fine-tuning of the algorithm will be carried out within the AC SAF project as soon as real data will be available. Improvements will be expected for the radiometric and calibration performances of the UVN payload; the description of surface reflectivity as function of the hourly-changing illumination; the filtering of cloudy pixels; and lastly the choice of a priori H₂O profiles.

2.4 Slant Column Density Retrieval

Typical absorption spectroscopy describes the attenuation properties of radiation along an optical path by the Beer-Lambert-Bouguer law. For satellite measurements, the equation can be written as:

$$I(\lambda) = I_0(\lambda) e^{\left(-\epsilon_m(\lambda) - \epsilon_R(\lambda) - L \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(\lambda) c_i\right)} R(\lambda) \quad (7)$$

$I_0(\lambda)$ refers to the direct sun irradiance spectrum taken at TOA, while $I(\lambda)$ is the Earthshine radiance in nadir direction measuring sunlight reflected by the Earth's surface and atmosphere. L represents the effective optical path length from TOA to the surface and back to the satellite. σ_i denotes the absorption cross section of gas i , and c_i is its average concentration along the effective optical path. ϵ_m and ϵ_R are the Mie and Rayleigh extinction integrated along the light path, respectively. $R(\lambda)$ represents reflectance. The spectral optical density can then be calculated by taking the logarithm of the ratio between $I_0(\lambda)$ and $I(\lambda)$ as:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \left(\frac{I_0(\lambda)R(\lambda)}{I(\lambda)} \right) \quad (8)$$

In practice Equation 1 cannot be directly applied for trace gas retrieval because the extinction by particles and gases are not yet quantified. The DOAS method is based on the assumption that atmospheric scattering processes show broadband spectral structures whereas gases exhibit narrow band absorption structures (e.g. Platt and Stutz, 2008). Therefore, the spectral optical density can be separated into narrow (or differential) $o(\lambda)$ and broad $b(\lambda)$ band contributions. The broadband contribution can be approximated by a low order polynomial $p(\lambda)$. The broadband structures in $R(\lambda)$ can also be accommodated by $p(\lambda)$ and narrowband $R(\lambda)$ features can be also included as pseudo cross-sections in the spectral fit. Thus, the equation can be rewritten as:

$$\tau(\lambda) = \tau'(\lambda) + \tau_b(\lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(\lambda) c_i + p(\lambda) \quad (9)$$

Characteristic absorption features of different trace gases are then used to determine their concentrations c_i along the effective optical path L .

Slant column densities of water vapour are retrieved by applying the DOAS spectral fitting technique. The SCD is defined as the integrated concentration along the optical path from TOA through the atmosphere to and reflected back to the satellite sensor ($L \times c_i$). The DOAS fit is initially applied to the wavelength range of 435 - 455 nm. The following absorption cross sections are employed: water vapour at 293 K from HITEMP database (Rothman et al., 2010) and scaled by Lampel et al. (2015), NO₂ at 220 K (Vandaele et al., 2002), O₃ at 228 K (Brionet et al., 1998), O₄ at 293 K (Thalman and Volkamer, 2013), and liquid water at 297 K (Pope and Fry, 1997) as well as a Ring spectrum. The broadband spectral structures caused by trace gas absorption, instrumental effects, Rayleigh and Mie scattering are removed by including a 4th order polynomial.

Shift and stretch parameters of radiance spectra are also fitted to compensate for the instability caused by thermal noise. Wavelength grids for backscattered radiance and solar irradiances might be slightly different due to the difference in viewing modes. Using the solar data as a baseline, this mismatch is treated by fitting shift and squeeze parameters to the backscattered radiance wavelength grid and re-sampling the measurements. Therefore, the DOAS fit has non-linear dependence on these shift and squeeze parameters, which is usually determined iteratively. In practice, spectral retrieval is performed iteratively to optimize the shift and squeeze parameters until a suitable convergence is reached.

Table 2: Summary of the water vapour slant column retrievals with different spectral fitting windows for TROPOMI measurements taken on 1st July 2018 (orbit 3698 - 3711) over the tropics (30°N – 30°S). Values for Sentinel-4 will be reassessed once real measurements are available.

Fitting Window	Width	Median SCD (kg m ⁻²)	Median RMS	Reference
430.0-450.0 nm	20.0 nm	40.01	6.94×10 ⁻⁴	Wagner et al. (2013)
430.0-480.0 nm	50.0 nm	35.70	7.19×10 ⁻⁴	Wang et al. (2014)
427.7-465.0 nm	37.3 nm	38.21	6.97×10 ⁻⁴	Wang et al. (2016)

432.0-466.5 nm	34.5 nm	38.01	6.67×10^{-4}	Wang et al. (2019)
427.7-455.0 nm	27.3 nm	40.45	7.05×10^{-4}	Chan et al. (2020)
435.0-455.0 nm	20.0 nm	39.96	6.41×10^{-4}	Chan et al. (2022)
435.0-455.0 nm	20.0 nm	TBD	TBD	Sentinel-4 ATBD

The spectral fitting window for the retrieval of water vapour slant columns is selected based on sensitivity study with TROPOMI measurements with different settings. The DOAS range and the water vapour slant column retrieval results are shown in Table 2. The median water vapour slant columns and the median root mean squares of spectral fit for measurements taken on 1st July 2018 (orbit 3698 - 3711) over the tropics (30°N - 30°N) are also shown. The range at 435.0 - 455.0 nm leads to the lowest RMS while the median SCD does not deviate from the average value computed otherwise. Therefore, the fit window 435 - 455 nm is chosen as the standard setting. An example of the DOAS retrieval of water SCD from a TROPOMI spectrum taken on 1st July 2018 over the Pacific Ocean is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: An example of DOAS retrieval of water vapour slant column for a TROPOMI spectrum taken on 1st July 2018 over the Pacific Ocean. Solar zenith and viewing zenith of 34.6° and 61.1°. The retrieved water vapour slant column is 89.8 kg m⁻² (Chan et al., 2020).

2.5 Air mass factors

The next step of the TCWV retrieval is the conversion of water vapour SCDs to vertical column densities (VCDs) (eg. Solomon et al., 1987). The VCD (or total column) is defined as the vertical integral of water vapour from the surface to TOA. As water vapour SCDs are retrieved within a relatively narrow spectral window, we can assume the wavelength dependency of the optical path is negligible. Thus, the AMFs need only be calculate at a representative wavelength. Due to the relatively strong water vapour absorption feature at 442 nm (see Section 2.6), the AMFs are calculated at this wavelength. The AMF can be expressed as:

$$AMF = \frac{SCD}{VCD} \quad (10)$$

Light travelling in the atmosphere can be scattered by air molecules, aerosols, and clouds. To resolve the optical path as well as the box air mass factor (ΔAMF), comprehensive multiple scattering radiative transfer calculations are required. The ΔAMF is defined as the AMF of each individual vertical layer. Typically, the height-dependent air mass factor can be decoupled from the vertical distribution of optically thin absorbers (Palmer et al., 2001). As a result, the AMF can then be calculated from the ΔAMF as:

$$AMF = \frac{SCD}{VCD} = \frac{\sum_{l=surface}^{l=TOA} \Delta AMF_l \times \Delta z_l \times c_l}{\sum_{l=surface}^{l=TOA} \Delta z_l \times c_l} \quad (11)$$

where Δz_l and c_l are the thickness and the number density of the absorber at layer l , respectively. c_l is taken from the a priori profile. The $\Delta AMFs$ are independent of the vertical distribution of the absorber but strongly dependent on viewing geometry, solar position, surface albedo and surface altitude.

The ΔAMF can be calculated using a radiative transfer model. To reduce the processing time, $\Delta AMFs$ are pre-calculated with a number of representative observation and solar geometries, surface albedo and surface pressure and stored in a look-up table. In the current version of retrieval algorithm, the ΔAMF look-up table is calculated with the radiative transfer model VLIDORT version 2.7 (Spurr, 2008) with an aerosol free US standard atmosphere (Anderson et al., 1986). The $\Delta AMFs$ for each particular TROPOMI observation can then be derived by interpolation. Details of the parameterization nodes of the ΔAMF look-up table are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameter nodes in the box air mass factor look-up table

Parameter (unit)	Symbol	# nodes	Grid values
Viewing zenith angle (°)	α	10	0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 65, 70, 75
Solar zenith angle (°)	θ	20	0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 72, 74, 76, 78, 80, 82, 84, 86, 88
Relative azimuth angle (°)	φ	7	0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180

Surface albedo	A_s	14	0, 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0
Surface pressure (hPa)	P_s	17	1063.10, 1037.90, 1013.30, 989.28, 965.83, 920.58, 876.98, 834.99, 795.01, 701.21, 616.60, 540.48, 411.05, 308.00, 226.99, 165.79, 121.11
Pressure level (hPa)	P_l	64	1056.77, 1044.17, 1031.72, 1019.41, 1007.26, 995.25, 983.38, 971.66, 960.07, 948.62, 937.31, 926.14, 915.09, 904.18, 887.87, 866.35, 845.39, 824.87, 804.88, 785.15, 765.68, 746.70, 728.18, 710.12, 692.31, 674.73, 657.60, 640.90, 624.63, 608.58, 592.75, 577.34, 562.32, 547.70, 522.83, 488.67, 456.36, 425.80, 396.93, 369.66, 343.94, 319.68, 296.84, 275.34, 245.99, 210.49, 179.89, 153.74, 131.40, 104.80, 76.59, 55.98, 40.98, 30.08, 18.73, 8.86, 4.31, 2.18, 1.14, 0.51, 0.14, 0.03, 0.01, 0.001

In the TCWV retrieval, linear interpolation is applied to the cosine of viewing zenith angle ($\cos \alpha$), cosine of solar zenith angle ($\cos \theta$), relative azimuth angle (φ) and surface albedo (A_s) dimensions, while nearest neighbour interpolation is used for the interpolation in the surface pressure (P_s) dimension. The viewing zenith angle, solar zenith angle and relative azimuth angle are taken from the level-1B product. Surface albedo is derived from TROPOMI observation at the same wavelength band using a full-physics inverse learning machine (FP_ILM) algorithm (see Section 2.6.1 Surface). The resulting ΔAMF profile is then linearly interpolated to match the vertical grid of water vapour a priori profile. The interpolated $\Delta AMFs$ are used to calculate the AMF.

The vertical distribution of water vapour is important for the SCD-to-VCD conversion. Most of the trace gas retrievals from satellite measurements in the UVVIS spectral range use vertical profile information from chemistry transport model simulations (e.g., Wang et al., 2014, 2016, Krotkov et al., 2017, De Smedt et al., 2018). Previous studies use a priori profile from GEOS-5 and MERRA-2 model products to retrieve TCWV from OMI observations (Wang et al., 2014, 2016). Here, we used the statistical analysis of historical profiles as a priori information, such that the influences from model simulation are greatly reduced and more suitable for climatological study. An iterative approach is employed to optimize the a priori water vapour vertical profile used in the satellite retrieval to make the satellite measurements independent from model simulations, and avoid propagating model errors into the measurement. It is based on the statistical analysis of water vapour vertical distribution over 11 years from 2008 to 2018.

Figure 12 shows the statistical analysis of water vapour profiles from ECMWF ERA-Interim reanalysis data (Dee et al., 2011; Berrisford et al., 2011) over a small region of Pacific Ocean (5°N-5°S, 170°-180°W) in July of 2008-2018. Water vapour profiles are sorted by their total column densities into 8 ranges from 20 kg m⁻² up to 60 kg m⁻². Colour coded lines indicate the mean profile of each range, while shadowed areas represent the 1 σ standard deviation variation of water vapour mixing ratio. The normalized mean profiles for each range are also indicated in Figure 3i.

These profiles are normalized by dividing their total columns and multiplying with the mean total column calculated from all measurements. The analysis result shows that water vapour vertical profile shapes are strongly related to their own column densities. Water vapour profiles with similar total columns show very similar vertical distribution. Water vapour is typically concentrated close to the surface below 800 hPa when the total column is small (less than 30 kg m⁻²). It starts to extend to higher altitudes with increasing total column and changes the profile shape. A much larger

portion of water vapour is located above 800 hPa when the total column is larger than 40 kg m⁻². The small standard deviation of the water vapour mixing ratio profile also indicates that the water vapour profile shape only varies slightly within each range.

Figure 12: Statistical analysis of climatological water vapour vertical profiles from ECMWF ERA-Interim data over Pacific Ocean (5°N-5°S, 170°-180°W) between 2008-2018. Water vapor profiles are grouped by ranges serving as a priori during the iterative conversion of SCD-to-VCD (Chan et al., 2020).

By making use of the fact that water vapour profile shapes are strongly correlated to their total columns, it becomes possible to compile a look-up table of water vapour vertical profile shapes. The chosen resolution adheres to that of the native low-resolution ECMWF data of 0.75°. Water vapour profiles are sorted into five ranges for each geolocation and for each month of the year. The mean profiles, the total columns, and the standard deviation of total columns for each range are stored and linearly interpolated to the satellite measurement location for each range. The iterative optimization of a priori water profiles begins by using the overall mean profile of the satellite measurement location of the corresponding month. This mean water vapour profile is then used together with the corresponding $\Delta AMFs$ to calculate an initial AMF . The SCD is divided by this

initial *AMF* to retrieve the initial vertical column. The look-up table is then linearly interpolated in the total column dimension to the retrieved initial column to retrieve the corresponding vertical profile shape. The interpolated profile is again used to retrieve the second vertical column. This process repeats until the difference between the input and output water vapour column is less than 1% or the number of iteration reaches the threshold limit. As the retrieval of more than 99% of TROPOMI measurements stopped within 3 iterations, the limit of maximum number of iteration in the current version of retrieval is set to 5.

2.6 Auxiliary data

2.6.1 Surface

The surface is a critical parameter in the calculation of the air mass factor. The sensitivity of satellite observations, particularly to the lower troposphere, where the majority of water vapor resides, is closely associated with the reflectivity of the surface. The reflectivity of the surface is typically characterized by albedo, which can be classified as either directional or hemispherical. Given the hourly observation design of Sentinel-4, it is advantageous to use hourly-changing surface albedo values while customary climatological values can be used as a fallback. There are two separate products foreseen to be tested for the Sentinel-4 water vapor product.

The first surface product relies on the ingestion of UVVIS radiances in the full-physics inverse learning machine (FP_ILM) algorithm, as applied to TROPOMI observations (Loyola et al., 2020). The training of the FP_ILM algorithm is driven by a set of synthetic data generated with a radiative transfer model. Synthetic (TROPOMI) radiance spectra at 435 – 455 nm are simulated using VLIDORT together with the smart sampling technique (Loyola et al., 2016). For the training, the inputs are the DOAS fitted parameters of the gas species under investigation, the angles defining the observational geometry and the surface pressure. The inversion result is the Geometry-dependent effective Lambertian equivalent reflectivity (GE_LER) and it is retrieved for clear sky observations (cloud fraction <0.05). The top panels of Figure 13 show the GE_LER values for January and July at the central wavelength (442 nm) of the water vapor algorithm for the full field of view of Sentinel-4. The bottom panels show the number of cloud-free scenes used to derive the surface albedo value.

The second product is the daily, hourly-resolved, official UVN-2-GSR (Gapless surface reflectance) containing the LER albedo, a unpolarized bidirectional reflectance function (BRF) described by the respective model coefficients, and an aerosol optical depth value ([RD09]).

Both surface products are expected to outperform the minimum Lambertian equivalent reflectivity (MLER) climatology derived from Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) observations (Kleipool et al., 2008), which is being used in most of the operational products, in characterizing the actual surface conditions, especially with regard to temporal variability.

Figure 13: Climatology of geometry-dependent equivalent Lambertian reflectivity of the surface at 442 nm and number of cloud-free pixels for January (a, c) and July (b,d). Values are computed following the GE_LER methods described in Loyola et al. (2020).

[Surface BRDF TBD]

2.6.2 Cloud properties

During the MTG-S mission, two different cloud products will be available for water vapor retrievals. They are the DLR OCRA/ROCINN cloud properties suite, based on UVN measurements, and the RAL/EUM FCS-CMA (with sub-products FCS-L1C ([RD10]), FCS-OCA ([RD11])) product, based on FCI data ([RD07]).

The first choice for the water vapor product is the DLR cloud properties (optical thickness/albedo, fraction and altitude/pressure) suite. They are retrieved with the OCRA (Lutz et al., 2016) and the ROCINN retrieval algorithms (Loyola et al., 2018). In the forward model, clouds can be parameterized either as opaque Lambertian surfaces (clouds as reflective boundaries – CRB) or as scattering layers (clouds as layers – CAL), the latter allowing light penetration and multiple scattering through the cloud body. Especially for cloud altitude/pressure differences between the two cloud parameterizations have to be expected. The treatment of partially cloudy pixels is based on the independent pixel approximation (Marshak et al., 1995, Martin et al., 2002, Boersma et al., 2004) where the pixel is separated into two independent parts, one with fully cloud cover and the other one is completely cloud free. Air mass factors are calculated separately for both clear sky and cloudy parts.

The cloudy AMF (AMF_{cloud}) is calculated from the ΔAMF look-up table by setting the surface pressure to cloud top pressure and replacing the surface albedo with the cloud albedo. It should be

noted that the same a priori water vapour profile is assumed in both the cloudy AMF and clear sky AMF (AMF_{clr}) calculations. The calculation of SCD for the cloudy scene is insensitive to water vapour below cloud and $\Delta AMFs$ below cloud are 0. On the other hand, VCD is calculated by integrating the water vapour profile from the surface to the top of atmosphere which includes the part below cloud. This ‘invisible’ column below the cloud (also known as ‘ghost column’) is taken from the a priori profile.

AMFs of partially cloudy pixels are calculated as the intensity weighted average of the AMF_{cld} and AMF_{clr} . This weighting is commonly known as intensity weighted cloud fraction (CF_{iw}) which is defined as:

$$CF_{iw} = \frac{CFR \times I_{cld}}{CFR \times I_{cld} + (1 - CFR) \times I_{clr}} \quad (12)$$

where I_{cld} and I_{clr} represents the radiance intensity for the cloudy and clear sky scenes, respectively. The radiance intensities are pre-calculated using VLIDORT at 442 nm for a number of representative observation and solar geometries, surface albedo, and surface pressure and stored in a look-up table. The settings of the intensity look-up table are the same as the ΔAMF look-up table but without the pressure level dimension. The AMF can then be calculated with:

$$AMF = AMF_{cld} \times CF_{iw} + AMF_{clr} \times (1 - CF_{iw}) \quad (13)$$

The resulting $AMFs$ are used to divide the measured slant columns to convert water vapour slant columns to vertical columns. This AMF is used for the iterative optimization of a priori profile of partially cloudy pixels.

The UVVIS and the NIR bands of Sentinel-4 are recorded on two different optical benches and a spatial misregistration in the North-South direction of up to $\frac{1}{4}$ ground pixel (approximately 2 km at sub-satellite central point) can be expected ([RD02]). This situation is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Spatial misregistration between the Sentinel-4 UVVIS (red) and NIR (blue) measurements. Six HSS measurements each Sentinel-4 ground pixel are available in the EW direction. FCI measurements give extra information along the NS direction.

In practice, every cloud or gas product relying on synergistic exploitation of both bands should be carefully interpolated. This is the case for cloud fraction derived in the UVVIS by OCRA, which

serves as input for the ROCINN algorithm in the NIR top derive cloud albedo and pressure. Once the intra-band misalignment is corrected for, the cloud properties have to be interpolated back to the original UVVIS spatial grid to allow accurate trace gas retrievals.

Two approaches can be devised: a baseline method and a more accurate method relying on the coincident and finer cloud information provided by co-located FCI cloud data within a time difference of 5 minutes for scan. The baseline method, applied and tested on TROPOMI data ([RD06]) is performed by using only the four corner coordinates given in the L1 geolocation and by finding the normalized area-weighted overlap between the source (UVVIS in this case) and target pixel (NIR). The weights scale then actual measurements. The second method uses re-gridded FCI data provided in the Sentinel-4-FCS product ([RD07]). In the event that the data is not available, the choice of the method for interpolation falls on the baseline implementation. More details on the exact steps to merge the UVVIS and NIR bands are found in the Sentinel-4 Cloud ATBD ([RD08]).

The second cloud product suite is based on FCI data and comprises cloud mask, altitude/pressure and optical thickness albedo ([RD07,RD10,RD11]). They rest on the imagery observations in the UVVIS, NIR and mid-infrared at substantially higher spatial resolution than Sentinel-4. They can be devised for additional applications such as: identification of cloud-free scenes, warranting additional sensitivity to the sub-visible cloud classes (e.g., thin, ice-phase, clouds); quantification of the geometric fraction of cloud within the Sentinel-4 field-of-view (FOV); radiometric cross-calibration of Sentinel-4; further refinement of Sentinel-4 products with synergetic exploitation in advanced algorithms.

The current water vapor product is designed to make use of the native CLD products derived from Sentinel-4 for consistency purposes with instrumental design and because of existing validation with Sentinel-5P.

2.6.3 Aerosols

The presence of aerosols affects the radiative transfer in the atmosphere and may influence the retrieval of surface properties, cloud and atmospheric water vapour (Bhatia et al., 2015, 2018). As the aerosol properties, e.g., extinction profile, single scattering albedo, asymmetry parameter, etc., are unknown, there is no general and easy solution to explicitly account for aerosols in the retrieval. On the other hand, it is very difficult to separate cloud and aerosol in the cloud retrieval due to their similarity in optical properties. As a result, the aerosol effect is already implicitly considered in the cloud product (Boersma et al., 2004, 2011). Therefore, no additional treatment of aerosol is applied in the water vapour retrieval algorithm.

2.6.4 Error estimation

The error of the TCWV is composed of many sources. Major sources of error can be divided into model and measurement errors. The uncertainty of the TCWV can be derived analytically through error propagation. As the TCWV retrieval is separated into two major steps, SCD and SCD-to-VCD conversion after AMF calculation, the error estimation also follows these two steps.

The uncertainty of TCWV can be express as:

$$\sigma_{vcd}^2 = VCD^2 \times \left(\left(\frac{\sigma_{scd}}{SCD} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{amf}}{AMF} \right)^2 \right) \quad (14)$$

where σ_{vcd} , σ_{scd} and σ_{amf} are the uncertainty of TCWV, the error of water vapour slant column, and air mass factor uncertainty, respectively.

The uncertainties of water vapour slant column are mainly attributed to instrumental noise, instrument characteristics, and the uncertainties related to the DOAS fit. Instrument noise is expected to show a random nature (Stutz and Platt, 1996). Other error sources such as fit of the slit function, stray light, wavelength calibration might contribute to the total error. Absorption cross sections and temperature dependency of the absorption cross sections contribute to the systematic component of the total SCD error and they are estimated through sensitivity tests with absorption cross section at different effective temperatures and slit functions. For TROPOMI, a systematic error of the slant column has been estimated to be 3%. The total error of the slant column can be calculated as:

$$\sigma_{vcd}^2 = \sigma_{scd,r}^2 + (0.03 + SCD)^2 \quad (15)$$

where $\sigma_{scd,r}^2$ is the random error estimated by analyzing the DOAS fit residual.

The uncertainty in the AMF is mainly related to the uncertainties of each input parameter used in the AMF calculation. These input parameters include the observational geometries, surface albedo and pressure, and water vapour vertical profile. The solar and viewing geometries are well calibrated and their errors are mainly related to the interpolation of the box AMF look-up table. These uncertainties are negligible compared to other sources of error. The contribution to the AMF uncertainty of the remaining sources of error can be estimated by the AMF sensitivity (or Jacobian) with respect to each parameter (Boersma et al., 2004). The Jacobian is derived from the box air mass factor look-up table using the finite difference method.

For TROPOMI, surface albedo is taken from the climatology monthly minimum Lambertian equivalent reflector (LER) product (Kleipool et al., 2008) at 442 nm derived from Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) satellite observations. The uncertainty of surface albedo (A_s) is assumed to be the difference between albedo derived at 425 nm and 442 nm to account for the small variation of albedo within the spectral fitting window. Information of surface pressure (P_s) is taken from a digital elevation model (DEM) which is considered rather accurate and the uncertainty of surface pressure is mostly related to the variation within the TROPOMI footprint. We have analyzed this variation of surface pressure and find it is mostly (95%) below 10 hPa. Therefore, we set the uncertainty of P_s to 10 hPa.

The error related to a priori vertical distribution of water vapour is determined by using the a priori water vapour from the last iteration plus 1σ standard deviation which is also included in the look-up table. This new profile is then used to calculate the corresponding AMF. The difference between this AMF and the original AMF is taken as the uncertainty from the a priori profile. The uncertainty of the water vapour slant column can potentially affect the dynamic search of the a priori profile. As the slant column uncertainty can be much higher than the slant column itself over dry areas in the upper latitudes, considering this effect in the vertical profile uncertainty estimation would further amplify the uncertainty and results in unrealistic high error. Therefore, we assume this effect is well covered by the vertical profile variation and accounted in the vertical profile uncertainty estimation. The error of the clear sky AMF can be calculated as:

$$\sigma_{amf,clr}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{clr}}{\partial A_s} \sigma_{A_s} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{clr}}{\partial P_s} \sigma_{P_s} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{clr}}{\partial c_l} \sigma_{c_l} \right)^2 \quad (16)$$

where $\sigma_{amf_{clr}}$, σ_{A_s} , σ_{P_s} and σ_{c_l} are the uncertainty of the clear sky AMF, surface albedo, surface pressure, and water vapor profile, respectively. This error is in general <5% for TROPOMI measurements over the tropics (30°N-30°S).

The calculation of the uncertainty of the cloudy AMF is similar to the one used for the clear sky AMF, with surface albedo and surface pressure uncertainties replaced by cloud albedo and cloud top pressure errors. In this study, cloud top pressure error is assumed to be 50 hPa (Theys et al., 2017; De Smedt et al., 2018). Previous studies show that the error of cloud albedo is compensated by the corresponding error of cloud fraction and results a negligible net effect on trace gas retrieval (Van Roozendael et al., 2006; Lutz et al., 2016). This is because from a spaceborne radiation perspective, a change in either cloud fraction or cloud albedo induce the same change in TOA reflectance sensed by the satellite. A cloud albedo and an intensity-weighted cloud fraction uncertainty of 0.02 are assumed. Their combined effect on water vapor retrieval is comparable to the assumption with just cloud fraction error of 0.05 (Theys et al., 2017; De Smedt et al., 2018). The error of the cloudy AMF can be express as:

$$\sigma_{amf_{cld}}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{cld}}{\partial A_c} \sigma_{A_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{cld}}{\partial P_c} \sigma_{P_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial AMF_{cld}}{\partial c_l} \sigma_{c_l} \right)^2 \quad (17)$$

where $\sigma_{amf_{cld}}$, σ_{A_c} , σ_{P_c} and σ_{c_l} are the uncertainty of the cloudy AMF, cloud albedo, cloud top pressure, and water vapour profile, respectively. The error of the cloudy AMF ($\sigma_{amf_{cld}}$) in general varies from 25% (25th percentile) to 40% (75th percentile) for TROPOMI measurements over the tropics (30°N-30°S).

The uncertainty in total AMF can be then derived from the clear sky and cloudy AMFs through error propagation. The error of the total AMF can be calculated with:

$$\sigma_{amf}^2 = (AMF_{cld} \times CF_{iw})^2 \times \left(\left(\frac{\sigma_{amf_{cld}}}{AMF_{cld}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{cf_{iw}}}{CF_{iw}} \right)^2 \right) + (AMF_{cld} \times (1 - CF_{iw}))^2 \times \left(\left(\frac{\sigma_{amf_{clr}}}{AMF_{clr}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{cf_{iw}}}{1 - CF_{iw}} \right)^2 \right) \quad (18)$$

where $\sigma_{cf_{iw}}$ is the uncertainty of intensity weighted cloud fraction which is assumed to be 0.02 in the retrieval. The uncertainty of AMF (σ_{amf}) varies in a range of 6-22% (25th and 75th percentile), while the error reduces to 6% if the measurements are filtered for intensity-weighted cloud fraction below 0.5. The AMF uncertainty shows a small latitudinal dependency on surface properties (albedo) and cloud patterns, observation and solar geometries. When all measurements are considered, the AMF uncertainty varies from 8% (25th percentile) to 24% (75th percentile) with median value of 16% while the mean error remains at 6% for measurements with intensity-weighted cloud fraction below 0.5. Combining the slant column density error with the AMF error, the estimated total TCWV error amounts, on average, to 19% under clear sky conditions (intensity weighted cloud fraction <0.5).

The TCWV product provides the corresponding averaging kernel for each ground pixel. The averaging kernel is the altitude-dependent AMF divided by the total air-mass factor. The averaging kernel is important for users who wish to minimise the discrepancies between the profile assumed in the retrieval and their application of interest, for example for validation, data assimilation, or model comparison to a model.

Quality assurance (QA) value is provided in the TCWV product. The QA value is determined based on observation geometry, measurement noise, cloud information and air mass factor. The QA value

varies between 0 (bad data) and 1 (good data). It is recommended that users not to use data with QA value below 0.5.

[TBD]

3. VALIDATION

[TBD]

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

[TBD]

F. REFERENCES

F.1 Reference documents

- [RD01] Sentinel-4 Level 2 Terms and symbols used in the ATBDs
source: DLR; **ref:** Sentinel-4-L2-DLR-ATBD-2019; **issue:** 1.0; **date:** 2017-05-31
- [RD02] Sentinel-4 Instrument Design
source: ESA; **ref:** Sentinel-4-L2-ESA-TEC-2016; **issue:** 1.0; **date:** 2016-04-13
- [RD03] Airbus_1 Bettina Oexl: GS4 - SENTINEL 4 UVN, 0 - Sentinel-4/UVN - CKD ATBD, DRL-No.: Sentinel-4-UV-35 , CI-No.: 0 – Sentinel-4/UVN, document_ID: GS4-ADSO-UVN-SP- 1000859597 Version 05, provided by: Olivier le Rille at ESA (October 2024)
- [RD04] Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document - GOME-2 Total Column Products of Ozone, NO₂, BrO, HCHO, SO₂, H₂O, OClO, and Cloud Properties (GDP 4.8 for GOME-2A&-B; GDP 4.9 for GOME-2C), Valks, P., Seo, S., Hedelt, Lelli, L., Lutz, R.,
source: DLR; **ref:** SAF/AC/DLR/ATBD/01; **issue:** 3/C; **date:** 2023-10
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source: DLR; **ref:** SAF/AC/DLR/PUM/01; **issue:** 3/C; **date:** 2023-10
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- [RD08] Sentinel-4 Level 2 ATBD Cloud
source: DLR; **ref:** Sentinel-4-L2-DLR-ATBD-2009; **issue:** 3.9; **date:** 2024-02-29
- [RD09] Sentinel-4 Level 2 ATBD Surface Reflectance and AOD (SUR)
source: LOA/CAT/RAY; **ref:** S4-L2-LOA_CAT_RAY-ATBD-2010
- [RD10] MTG-FCI: ATBD for Cloud Mask and Cloud Analysis Product
source: Eumetsat; **ref:** EUM/MTG/DOC/10/0542; **issue:** v4; **date:** 2015-10-16
- [RD11] MTG-FCI: ATBD for Optimal Cloud Analysis Product
source: Eumetsat; **ref:** EUM/MTG/DOC/11/0654; **issue:** v4; **date:** 2011-10-24

F.2 Peer-reviewed articles

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